

A De-Convolution Technique used for NDE on laminated sample in X-ray & industrial-CT

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ABSTRACT -

A De-Convolution Technique for the detection and enhancement of image edge-profiles to the sub-pixel accuracy without any trade-off loss has been found. Enhancement via the removal of the Penumbra Effect within a zoomed sub-pixel space is carried out empirically via sub-pixel transfers and under the spatial bandwidth control of a global Line-Spread-Function that no ambiguity is introduced. Phantom calibrations and field NDT examples in X-ray and CT were used to demonstrate its merits i.e. in both the improved spatial resolution in image and the improved accuracy to the sub-pixel level in measurements. Clearer diagnosis in image and accurate measurements have been achieved by using this methodology, which may lead to the finding of a definitive method used in Quantitative Radiology in NDT. Its key applications is in the accurate quantitative assessment or monitoring of fracture(s) or minute defect(s) or corrosion under any mechanical stress or strain or the chemical corrosion process.

Keywords -

X-ray, CT, Image, Enhancement, Deconvolution, Technique, NDT

Background -

(1) History of the Problem - Blurred image-edges caused by the 'Penumbra Effect' have existed since the discovery of X-ray (that led to its Radiography) in 1895. Even in Computed Tomography (CT), the combined effect of the size of the energy source and/or the size of the detector(s) still result in the 'Penumbra Spread' problem.

(2) Previous Work -

(a) The hardware solution to the problem involves the collimation of the photon beam, which reduces the dose efficiency and results in an increase in image noise (Ref. [2]).

(b) Prior related works

In 1989, Alperin worked on the "Automatic Analysis of Coronary Lesions from Cineangiograms using Vessel Tracking and Iterative De-Convolution Technique [3]. Charland recovered the Line Spread Function of Radiation Detector using the De-Convolution Technique [4]. Marsudi used an edge model derived by convolving a signal with energy filters to extract 2D edge feature to sub-pixel accuracy [5]. Smith used two-dimensional De-Convolution Technique to remove the blurred edges for small spatial measurement in X-ray Radiography [6]. Keller used the upper and lower CT contrast threshold to determine the edge-profile(s) for the outlining of its contour [7]. Chui used the De-Convolution Technique to measure the slice-thickness in MR scan [8]. Numerous medical applications by CAD based

on the De-Convolution Technique have also been realized by Chui et.al. [9]. Chui et.al. published 'A De-Convolution Technique used for Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) in X-ray & CT' [10] which brought about the change of unit of specification from 'pixel accuracy' to 'sub-pixel accuracy' by the International Committee for Non-Destructive Testing (ICNDT).

With the exception of [10], none of the other methods above plus other enhancement methodologies involved entering the magnified sub-pixel domain to improve the spatial resolution. Actually, they all operate in the pixel domain and therefore have the minimum experimental tolerance of +/-1 pixel, which are two pixels across. From a CT phantom calibration, the mean Penumbra Effect was measured to be in the range of 2.0 – 2.4 pixels across the blurred region (explained in a later section). It is, therefore, practically impossible to remove the Penumbra Effect using any other methods, which only operate inside a pixel domain, which have the experimental error of two pixels across in average.

(3) The Solution detailed in this Study -

In each image matrix, there are two components of spatial resolution. The first one is the spatial resolution defined by the pixel size, or more specifically, by the reciprocal of the distance (i.e. in number of pixel modulation per distance) between adjacent pixels. The maximum of which, is the diagonal spatial resolution at forty-five degree angle. Its vector direction is along the edge-profile of contrast. The second component of spatial resolution is orthogonal to the first one. This second component of spatial resolution is most affected by the Penumbra Effect. Nevertheless, it is often the second component of spatial resolution plus the signal-to-noise (e.g. the voxel size) consideration that determines the selection of the pixel size for the first component. In Physics, one may independently improve or change the property of one orthogonal vector without affecting the other vector orthogonal to it.

The main purpose of this study is to improve the second component of spatial resolution by the elimination or the correction of the Penumbra Effect.

Our current solution -

Recently, using the processing power of modern CPUs, an innovative software solution to the problem without any trade-off increase in image noise has been founded. It is a post-processing De-Convolution Technique for the detection, definition and enhancement of image edge-profiles. Sub-pixel sampling at the Nyquist frequency was used to preserve the spatial resolution of the first component. The detection of true edge-positions and enhancement of edge-profiles via sub-pixel transfer were carried out in the magnified sub-pixel domain to improve the spatial resolution of the second component, which is most affected by the Penumbra Effect.

Enhancement is carried out in a magnified space with magnification factor of 3, 5, 7, or 9. The upper limit of magnification factor of 9 was used due to the 1/10th pixel of experimental error at 1% low-contrast noise limitation (refer to Evaluation & Results section). Within this zoomed span of 3 to 9, the higher the magnification factor, the clearer is the enhanced image obtained, as both the Penumbra Effect and the Pixelization Effect are overcome at the same time by the re-processing. By solving this previously 'unsolvable' century-old problem without any trade-off loss, numerous important applications may now be realized.

The Principle of the De-Convolution Technique -

Figure 1

Due to the size of the energy source, detector size for some imagers and other second order factors such as contrast level, noise spike, overshoots, and local partial volume effects, a Delta Function in the Object Domain cannot be reproduced in the Image Domain. Instead, a “local” Line Spread Function (LSF) of a specific shape is obtained. Similarly, a specific-shaped “local” ‘blurred’ Edge Response Function (ERF) is obtained from the Step Function (SF) of an object (Figure 1). This specific-shaped ‘blurred’ ERF varies from edge-position to edge-position. The blurred feature may be described as the “Blooming Effect” of varying windows settings, which is mainly caused by the above ‘Penumbra Spread’ Problem. Mathematically, the ERF can be derived by the Convolution of the LSF with the SF (Figure 1 & the Mathematical Model). Experimentally; we may derive the “local” LSF from the ERF by the De-Convolution Process

using a Running Filter Technique (Figure 1 & Mathematical Model). By overlaying the "local" LSF over its specific-shaped ‘blurred’ ERF, the true edge position is calculated from the mid-point of the full-width-half-maximum (FWHM) to sub-pixel accuracy (Figures 1, 2 & 3). Sub-pixels from the low-contrast side of the edge can then be transferred over to the higher-contrast side of the edge to restore, empirically, the original SF feature and to enhance the image-edge without any increase in image noise. The processes of the De-Convolution and enhancement are both carried out under the strict spatial bandwidth controls of a global LSF that no ambiguity is introduced.

Figure 2 - Example: LSF derived from ERF

Figure 3 - Example: Magnified section

Enhancement is carried out by the empirical transfer of sub-pixels from the low-end of the edge over to the high-end to restore the high-resolution feature at each edge position of the edge-profile without any trade-off loss, which may result in any increase in image-noises. Both the De-Convolution and Reconstruction processes are carried out under the strict spatial bandwidth controls of a global LSF so that no ambiguity such as the gradual slope profile is detected.

All the edge-detection, enhancement and operational functionalities are incorporated into a Computer Aided Detection (CAD) software package via a DICOM toolkit.

Mathematical Model - The mathematical models of the Convolution and then the De-Convolution are described as follows:-

De-Convolution

Mathematical Model -

Convolution -

At Point 1: $\sum_{1}^{a} L(x) \Delta x = E(x)_1$

“ “ “ “ “ “

At Point n: $\sum_{1}^{a} L(x) \Delta x - \sum_{a-(n-1)}^{a} L(x) \Delta x = E(x)_n$ where $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ or n .

De-Convolution -

Between Point 1 \rightarrow Point 2:

$$E(x)_1 - E(x)_2 = \sum_{a-1}^{a} L(x) \Delta x = \{L(x)_a - L(x)_{(a-1)}\} \Delta x$$

or $\{E(x)_1 - E(x)_2\} / \Delta x = L(x)_a - L(x)_{(a-1)}$

Leading to:- Between Point (n-1) \rightarrow Point n:

$$\{E(x)_{n-1} - E(x)_n\} / \Delta x = L(x)_n - L(x)_{(n-1)} \quad \text{where } n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \text{ or } n.$$

Evaluation and Results -

Phantom of contrast edge was scanner examined. Optimal accuracy and sensitivity of the methodology could be achieved via the optimization of parameters used. Nyquist sub-pixel sampling criteria were imposed to ensure the full extraction of the 'cut-off' spatial resolution of the first type. In *Figure 2 – Example: LSF derived from ERF*, the 'step-shape' feature of the pixel data of the Edge Response Function (ERF) of the contrast edge was reduced to the 'smooth' feature of the derived LSF due to the smoothing effect of the Running Filter. The length of the Running Filter of the De-Convolution could be lengthened (increasing smoothing to reduce noise) or shortened (to increase the sensitivity). Further averaging is made by calculating the mid-point of the full-width-half-maximum (FWHM) of the LSF to achieve the sub-pixel accuracy (Figure 2 illustrates the intercept of the normal vector of the mid-point of FWHM with the X-axis).

In *Figure 3* – several edge-positions via the X-sweep (solid black circles) and Y-sweep (white rings) were sampled to form the edge-profile as indicated by the solid black line through the edge-positions. The two arrows indicate the extent of the "blurring" at the original ERFs., which was measured to be 2.4 pixels in average. The smooth edge-profile indicated the accuracy to the sub-pixel level as well as the feature of the edge-profile 'after' its enhancement. It is quite apparent that the effect of enhancement 'can only be visualized' or 'with properties accurately measured' within the magnified sub-pixel space domain.

2) Calibrations - A New York Catphan 500 was examined using Single Slice helical CT using technique factors of 120kVp, 300mA, 4 secs., 10mm slice.

Distance, area, and volume calibrations, high & low contrast resolutions, and processing time were studied:

(i) Distance, Area and Volume Measurements

Distance – At high-contrast & 1% low-contrast edge, accurate to $1/50^{\text{th}}$ of a pixel in $(\Delta)r$ (i.e. $(\Delta)r$ in $(\Delta)r/r$); and,

Area/Volume – At high-contrast & 1% low-contrast edge, accurate to $1/18^{\text{th}}$ & $1/10^{\text{th}}$ of a pixel in $(\Delta)r$ (i.e. $2(\pi)r(\Delta)r/(\pi)r^2$ or $(\Delta)(\text{area}) = 2(\pi)r(\Delta)r$)

(Volume = Area x Slice-thickness).

(ii) High Contrast Resolution

Mean Modulation Transfer Function (MTF) at the high contrast Teflon edge were improved from 3.38 lp/cm to 7.75, 8.94, 9.61 and 10.04 lp/cm at 50% normalized modulation level and from 5.83 lp/cm to 11.89, 13.90, 15.03, and 15.75 lp/cm at 10% normalized modulation level respectively after 3x, 5x, 7x and 9x magnification and enhancement. The calculations were made by the method of P. Judy [11].

(iii) Low-Contrast Resolution

(a) Resolved 1% low contrast rod down to 3mm at 50mA;4 secs;120 kVp;5mm slice; or

(b) Well-resolved 0.3% low contrast to 2mm rod at 300mA, 120kVp;4 secs;10mm slice.

(iv) Processing Time

At 3x, 5x, 7x, 9x magnification of Region of Interest (ROI) (i.e. 107x107, 64x64, 46x46, & 36x36 matrix respectively), it took 4.67, 0.98, 0.43, 0.29 seconds by a 600 MHz CPU and 1.17, 0.25, 0.11, and 0.07 seconds by a 2.4 GHz CPU respectively.

(v) Limitation

The De-Convolution Technique works well at the medium to high-contrast edges but less well at the low-contrast edges, particularly in a noisy image. - The large noise grains of a noisy image will cause the 'zig-zag' feature at the edge-profile.

There are three possible ways to overcome this limitation:-

(1) In NDT, use higher tube potential, kVp, to produce the more penetrating X-ray for a better signal-to-noise radiography image, and,

(2) A noise filter was designed for uses (the use of a noise filter may smoothen out some useful high spatial frequency information).

3) Field-Examples -

(A) A phantom was used:- X-ray radiogram of a Guide wire was used to demonstrated the removal of the Penumbra Effect Figures 4, 5, and 6 showed the original image of the phantom with the region of interest (ROI) placed on the Guide wire. The absolute measurements made via a calibrated object were: manufacturer's specification, $d=0.89\text{mm}$, measured value, $d'=0.91\text{mm}$; Error= $+2.25\%$;

(B) Digitally scanned CT scan image of fiberglass section (120kVp, 28mA) image was analyzed. Defects were enhanced (Figures 7-9);

(C) Micro-CT scan image of 3D woven dry fabric made of monofilament polyester yarns used in forming section in paper machine was analyzed. Figures 10, 11, 12, 13 showed the original image with ROI, 9xROI 'before' enhancement, 9xROI 'after' enhancement, and 9xROI 'after' enhancement with edge-profiles respectively. Blurred regions between filaments but still with small modulations were separated after the enhancement. Edge-dot profiles of Figure 13 may be fed into a 3D finite-element mesh for mechanical studies. For the regions, which did not have any modulations left, enhancement could not separate them, and manually input edge-dots will have to be added in to separate them for the 3D finite-element mesh, and,

(D) Micro-CT scan image of 3D-Woven Carbon (PAN-based) fiber wrapped around a tubing was used for analyses:-

- (i) ROI-1 of filaments lying along the scan plane was analyzed. Figures 14, 15, 16 & 17 showed the original image with ROI-1, 9xROI-1 'before' enhancement, 9xROI-1 'after' enhancement, and 9xROI-1 'after' enhancement with edge-profiles, and,
- (ii) ROI-2 of filaments perpendicular to the scan plane was analyzed. Figures 18, 19, 20 & 21 showed the original image with ROI-2, 9xROI-2 'before' enhancement, 9xROI-2 'after' enhancement, and 9xROI-2 'after' enhancement with edge-profiles.

In both (i) & (ii), sharp edge-profiles were obtained after the enhancement. The edge-profiles may be fed into a 3D finite-element mesh for further mechanical studies.

Conclusion –

The ERF-blurring or “penumbra-spread” can not be overcome by current digital enhancement as its true edge position is not located. But this deconvolution technique permits sensitive and accurate edge-profile detection and enhancement to overcome the century old “penumbra-spread” problem without any trade-off loss, which may result in noise increase.

Invisible and barely visible minute fractures or effects were enhanced to clearly visible for accurate diagnosis and measurements for the quantitative assessment in various applications.

For example, it is useful in:

- (1) to accurately monitor minute fractures or defects under mechanical stress or strain in industrial applications; and,
- (2) to feed the edge-dot coordinates into a 3D finite element mesh for the mechanical studies.

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Images – Figure 1 – the De-Convolution Technique; Figure 2 – LSF derived from ERF; Figure 3 – Magnified Section; Figure 4 – Original image of guide wire & coin phantom; Figure 5 – Guide wire 'before' enhancement; Figure 6 – 9x ROI – Guide wire 'after' enhancement; Figure 7: Original image of helicopter blade with ROI.; Figure 8: 5x ROI on defects 'before' enhancement; Figure 9: 5x ROI on defects 'after' enhancement; Figure 10: Original image of 71XXA-1 with ROI; Figure 11: 9x ROI on 71XXA-1 'before' enhancement; Figure 12: 9x ROI on 71XXA-1 'after' enhancement; Figure 13: 9xROI on 71XXA-1 'after' enhancement with edge-profiles; Figure 14: Original image of Slice111a* with ROI-1; Figure 15: 9x ROI-1 of Slice111a* 'before' enhancement; Figure 16: 9xROI-1 of Slice111a* 'after' enhancement; Figure 17: 9xROI of Slice111a* 'after' enhancement with edge profiles; Figure 18: Original image of Slice111a* with ROI-2; Figure 19: 9x ROI-2 of Slice111a 'before' enhancement; Figure 20: 9x ROI-2 of Slice111a* 'after' enhancement; and, Figure 21: 9x ROI-2 of Slice111a* 'after' enhancement with edge-profiles.

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Figure 4: Original image of guide wire & coins with ROI.

Figure 5: 9x ROI on guide wire 'before' enhancement.

Figure 6: 9x ROI on guide wire 'after' enhancement.

Figure 7: Original image of helicopter blade with ROI.

Figure 8: 5x ROI on defects 'before' enhancement.

Figure 9: 5x ROI on defects 'after' enhancement.

Figure 10: Original image of 71XXA-1 with ROI.

Figure 11: 9x ROI on 71XXA-1 'before' enhancement.

Figure 12: 9x ROI on 71XXA-1 'after' enhancement.

Figure 13: 9x ROI 'after' enhancement with edge-profiles.

Figure 14: Original image of Slice111a with ROI-1.

Figure 15: 9x ROI-1 of Slice111a 'before' enhancement.

Figure 16: 9xROI-1 of Slice111a 'after' enhancement

Figure 17: 9xROI 'after' enhancement with edge profiles

Figure 18: Original image of Slice111a with ROI-2.

Figure 19: 9x ROI-2 of Slice111a 'before' enhancement.

Figure 20: 9x ROI-2 of Slice111a 'after' enhancement.

Figure 21: 9x ROI-2 'after' enhancement with edge-profiles